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A Cooperative Intersection Support Application enabled by SAFE STRIP Technology both for C-ITS equipped, non-equipped and autonomous vehicles

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Problems addressed and motivations: INTERSECTIONS

- A great portion of all car **accidents** involves intersections
- **Compensate** lack of attention, understanding, visibility, and even lack of caution.
- Cooperate with autonomous vehicles
- **Provide warnings** with enough anticipation
- **Provide maneuvers** for autonomous vehicles
- Address mixed environments
- Extension of “e2call” Co-Driver [1]

Inference - Mirroring approach

- A mirroring agent is able both to perform **driving** tasks and use them to **interpret** his/her driving intentions.
- Possible and **usable** longitudinal maneuvers are calculated
- Warning are generated basing on the **potential** maneuvers

Hierarchical approach

2 layers: Intersection management and manoeuvre generation

Action priming: Manoeuvres

- Atomic longitudinal maneuvers: **Longitudinal motion primitives**
- Derived **minimizing the jerk.**
- Longitudinal Jerk as **control input.**
- **Warnings if the jerk is too high**
- From Co-Driver of [1]
- manoeuvre sets:
Stop and **Pass**
- **Pass** according to **time slots**

Trajectory: Clothoids

- **Clothoids** are human doable manoeuvres
- Curvature according to the 2/3 law[2]

Intersection management

- Objective is to find **time slots** for each vehicle
- This can run **independently** on each vehicle (decentralized)
- All the possibilities are taken into account (conservative approach)

Time slot calculation: 1

1. Define a **conflict area**
2. Compute **all possible** trajectories
3. Each manoeuvre is considered as a **virtual different vehicle**
4. Calculate **conflicts** between them
5. Assign **priorities** by the RoW Matrix

$$R_w = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & +1 & +1 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & -1 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ +1 & +1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Time slots calculation: 2

6. The **first vehicle** has time slots depending on the manuevres only
7. Every vehicle consider the **higher priority vehicles** time slots and **time to cross**
8. Its **own time to cross** is also taken into account
9. obtained **final time slots** feeds the action priming layer

Simulation and use cases

- Use case: T intersection

- 2 scenarios: **all autonomous** and **two autonomous and one unfair driver**

Results: all autonomous

- 6 possible conflicts
- Randomly generated vehicles and I.C.
- Manuever chosen in pass set if possible
- **No overlapping in passing**
- 50 simulations

Results: mixed environment

- The driver is simulated to arrive at constant velocity
- Warning is **issued** → driver **reacts**
- **Anticipation** is measured (Time To Intersection)
- **Yellow** vehicle is the driver

Conclusions and future work

- A **systematic decentralized approach** to deal with conflicts using time slots, which takes into account also the traffic rules is proposed.
- The consistency of the manoeuvres generated is **validated in simulation** as well as the anticipatory characteristics of the warnings.
- The approach can be used to **generate warnings** with enough anticipatory characteristics or to generate maneuvers for autonomous vehicles.
- Future work can be about **experimental validation**, or simulation introducing more uncertainties.

Thanks for your attention!

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References

1. Cooperative Intersection Support System Based on Mirroring Mechanisms Enacted by Bio-Inspired Layered Control Architecture (Da Lio, Mazzalai, Darin)
2. On Curve Negotiation: From Driver Support to Automation (Bosetti , Da Lio , Saroldi)